

DESIGN, FABRICATION, INSTALLATION, AND TESTING OF A TRIPLE-BOX GIRDER COMPOSITE STRUCTURE

M. Zoghi, D.C. Foster, and D.R. Bowman

University of Dayton

Dayton, Ohio 45469-0243, USA

SUMMARY: Throughout the 1990's, the Air Force Research Laboratory's Materials Directorate located at Wright-Patterson Air Force Base, in collaboration with the Butler County's Engineer's Office, Martin Marietta Materials, and the consulting firm of Lockwood, Jones, and Beals, Inc., initiated a research and development (R&D) program to transfer technology in advanced composite materials, originally developed for aerospace applications to the civilian community. The culmination of this team effort was a series of bridge rehabilitation projects utilizing fiber reinforced polymer (FRP) composite materials first, and then design and construction of an all-composite vehicular bridge, christened the "Tech-21" Bridge.

Tech-21 Bridge, located on Smith Road near Hamilton, Ohio, is 33 ft (10.1 m) long, 24 ft (7.3m) wide, weighs less than 22,000 lb, with a depth of 2 ft 9 inches including a wearing surface of asphalt, 5.5 in. (14 cm) at the center decreasing to 2.5 in. (6.4 cm) at the edges. The structure consists of a sandwich deck, constructed from pultruded tubes, which are between laminated face sheets. The deck is bonded to three longitudinal U-shaped structural beams. The integral superstructure beams, fabricated over timber forms with E-Glass fibers and a polyester resin, employed a wet lay-up process. The prefabricated sections were delivered to the job site via a flat-bed semi-trailer truck, where a 30-ton crane was utilized to lift the sections and set them in place. The entire installation process required only three hours on the morning of July 8, 1997.

Tech21 Bridge, considered to be the nation's first fully instrumented all-composite vehicular bridge, consists of an extensive health-monitoring system totaling over 120 permanent sensors, which were installed during its fabrication. These sensors have been monitoring strains and ambient temperatures at critical locations on the bridge and moisture absorption along the bond line since its inception. Foster-Miller was contracted to install advanced fiber-optic sensors, whereas, the Bridge Diagnostics, Inc. (BDI) was responsible for installation of conventional sensors. The University of Dayton, in collaboration with other parties involved in R&D of the Tech-21 Bridge, assumed the responsibility of long-term health monitoring and durability characteristics of the structure under sponsorship of Federal Highway Administration (FHWA). Several full-scale live-load tests have been conducted during summer and winter to characterize the structural performance under different ambient conditions. An overview of the design, fabrication, and installation of the Tech-21 Bridge will be presented, along with the compilation of field data obtained throughout the life of structure. The bridge and associated health monitoring system were a joint venture among industry, government, and academe. Herein lies another objective of the proposed manuscript; i.e., to present a historical perspective of the technology transfer from aerospace industry to civil infrastructure in the context of a prototype project.

KEYWORDS: fiber-reinforced polymer (FRP) composites, durability, health-monitoring, pultrusion, technology-transfer.

INTRODUCTION

The deteriorating state of bridges in the National Bridge Inventory (NBI) and the high cost of traditional construction materials have challenged civil engineering community to investigate alternative methods to repair and replace the existing bridges. Conventional materials such as steel, reinforced and prestressed concrete, used in construction of bridge infrastructure, are losing the battle against corrosion worldwide caused by the de-icing salts, marine salts, and environmental pollutants [4]. In the case of reinforced and prestressed concrete bridges, the concrete is crumbling, leaving the reinforcing steel and prestressing strands exposed and subject to rusting. In addition, the increased daily traffic and truck weights, along with more frequent overloads and insufficient maintenance, repairs and problem of aging, inflict compounding impact on these vital transportation links. As a result, nearly 28% of the existing 590,984 bridges in the NBI are considered to be structurally deficient or functionally obsolete [1].

Although the number of aforementioned deficient bridges has declined, the amount of bridge expenditures continues to rise [2]. Cooper, et al [2], stipulate that the Nation spends at least \$5 billion for the highway bridge design, construction, replacement, and rehabilitation annually. It is well known that the continued economic strength and growth of the Nation is intimately linked to the state of structural health and reliability of roadway and bridge infrastructure. This was particularly evident in the aftermath of September 11th horrific event since the public opted to travel by automobiles, mass transit, or other modes of transportation in lieu of traveling by air due to security concerns. The already overburdened roads and bridges became even more congested – at least for a short time.

In view of the above quandary, “the Federal Highway Administration (FHWA) is committed to a significant reduction in the number of deficient bridges in the Nation and a reduction in times and cost necessary to complete new bridges and bridge improvement projects,” infer Hooks, et al [5]. Furthermore, Hooks, et al, affirm, “the FHWA supports innovative bridge programs which deploy state-of-the-art technology to help achieve that goal.” One such innovative technology is the use of the Fiber-Reinforced Polymer (FRP) Composites for both bridge rehabilitation repair and new construction. It is recognized that FRP Composites, successfully utilized in the aircraft and boating industries for several decades, present numerous advantages over the conventional construction materials such as steel and concrete. These novel materials offer a variety of benefits regarding their selection and use including light-weight, high strength-to-weight ratio, directional strength, corrosion resistance, weather resistance, dimensional stability (i.e., low thermal conductivity and coefficient of thermal expansion), nonmagnetic, radar transparency, high dielectric strength (insulator), low maintenance, low-term durability, parts construction, small-to-large part geometry possible, tailored surface finish, and high impact strength/resistance [6].

A number of large-scale demonstration composite bridge projects have been initiated around the world recently. The Ohio’s first all-composite vehicular bridge, christened the Tech 21 Bridge, is an ideal example of such a demonstration project. The Tech 21 Bridge, a unique public-private partnership, was installed in July 1997. The bridge is located on Smith Rd., in the City of Hamilton, in Butler County, Ohio. Distinct features of the Tech 21 Bridge including geometric and material characteristics, design, fabrication, and construction will be presented in this manuscript. Furthermore, several short-term load tests have been conducted to date. A summary of load-test results along with the long-term durability of the bridge superstructure will be discussed as well.

GEOMETRIC AND MATERIAL PROPERTIES

A schematic diagram of the Tech 21 Bridge is exhibited in Figure 1. The two-lane, single-span superstructure has an overall length of 33'-0" (10.1 m). The width of the bridge is equal to 24'-0" (7.3 m), face-to-face of guardrails. The bridge consists of three trapezoidal beams supporting the deck. Each individual beam is 25.2 in. (64 cm) deep, 30.6 in. (77.7 cm) wide at the bottom and 46.5 in. (118.1 cm) wide at the top, respectively. The exterior beams are located 7'-6" (2.3 m) from the center of the interior beam, which is placed in the middle. The overall bridge deck thickness is 7.2 in. (18.3 cm), yielding a superstructure depth of 32.4 in. (82.3 cm).

Figure 1. Cross-section of the Assembled GFRP Structure and Asphalt Concrete Wear Surface.

The material chosen for fabrication of the Tech 21 Bridge consists of continuous E-glass fiber embedded in a matrix of polyester/vinyl ester [3]. The factors influencing the selection of this material was in part due to lower cost, availability, ease of fabrication, and “insensitivity to minor composition and processing variations,” specify [3].

The pertinent specifications and data on fiber composite materials are furnished in the Appendix 5 of Reference [3]. Accordingly, the 5.5 in. (14 cm) thick sandwich-construction with the upper and lower face-sheets possessing 56 oz. knitted fiberglass fabric [0° / 45° / 90° / -45° / mat] lay-up, unsaturated two-plate polyester and one-plate vinylester resins, co-boned core made from pultruded sections [3].

The bridge superstructure is fabricated in three major components for ease of transportation. The cross-sections of the individual components are exhibited in Figure 2. Each individual component includes a U-beam, bonded to a section of the deck. The centerpiece comprises an additional support plate facilitating the attachment of the narrow deck section to the beam. Bolts were used to clamp the beams to the deck sections to ensure full contact for the adhesive between the deck and the top flanges of the beams. Furthermore, a polyester gelcoat, containing ultra violet radiation inhibitors, was applied to all exposed surfaces.

Figure 2. Cross-Sections of Three Bridge Components.

INSTALLATION

The Tech 21 Bridge was delivered to the job site via a flat-bed semi-trailer truck. The centerpiece was placed first utilizing a 30-ton crane. Following the application of a two-part adhesive to the flanges of the centerpiece, the exterior sections were set in place and aligned. The segments were clamped together by bolts. The entire installation time of the superstructure was approximately four hours. The total construction time for the replacement of the existing bridge was about six weeks.

Modified type-1 steel posts with a deep beam rail and tubular backup comprised the guardrails for this project [3]. Appropriate connections, designed for the bolts to yield prior to the deck failure, were adopted to transfer loads into the top and bottom skins of the deck. Moreover, an asphalt concrete (AC) wearing surface was placed following the application of a bituminous tack coat to the FRP composite deck. It varied in thickness from 5.5 in. (14 cm) at the crown to 2.5 in. (6.4 cm) near the edges.

DESIGN CONSIDERATIONS

The design of Tech 21 Bridge was in accordance with the AASHTO Specifications based on HS20-44 loading and a maximum live load deflection limited to $\text{span}/800$ [8]. As a result, the bridge has a relatively high factor of safety ($FS=4.0$) with respect to strength. The computed stresses, based on the high factor of safety applied to the design loads, are compared to the “first ply failure criterion,” which is considered to be extremely conservative [8].

The peak dead load deflection of the bridge deck, under the weight of the superstructure alone (approximately 21,000 lb), was equal to 0.05 in., with negligible induced stresses [3, 8]. The estimated maximum deflection of the bridge subjected to the combination of the weight of the structure and the initial AC wearing surface of 50 psf amounts to 0.174 in. The estimated peak deflection increases to about 0.325 in. when a contingency for superimposing an additional AC wearing surface of 60 psf. It should be noted that the support beams were initially cambered by 0.5 in. during fabrication to compensate the sustained dead load deflection. Finite element analysis (FEA) was employed to verify the strength and deflection performance of the bridge and to determine the stress distribution throughout the bridge. The results of the FEA along with the Tsai-Hill parameters are given in [8].

SUMMARY OF LOAD TEST RESULTS AND HEALTH-MONITORING PLAN

A unique feature of the Tech 21 Bridge is the extensive instrumentation system that was installed on the structure during various stages of fabrication. Accordingly, 27 strain gages, 12 displacement sensors, 3 tilt meters, and 6 level meters along with 51 temperature sensors, all based on vibrating wire technology, were mounted throughout the bridge. The ambient temperature and relative humidity are monitored as well.

An advanced composite bridge health-monitoring system including 20 sensors, based on fiber optic technology, was also installed on the Tech 21 Bridge during its fabrication [10]. Specifically, two of the sensors were installed to monitor the bond-lines between the bridge segments for moisture incursion, whereas the remaining 18 sensors were placed to measure material strains.

A data logger was utilized to monitor the permanent sensors described above. The system was programmed to download the data remotely via a telephone line. This system served the basic structural health-monitoring of the bridge since its inception in July 1997. Each individual sensor was read once a minute. The sensor readings would be averaged over a 1-hour period and stored in the data logger's long-term memory. The collected data would be downloaded remotely via a telephone line weekly.

The aforementioned health-monitoring system has enabled the long-term performance-assessment of the Tech 21 Bridge continuously by measuring the structural response to vehicular loading and temperature changes over daily and yearly cycles. A representative sensor reading, exhibiting the temperature variation versus time, is provided in Figure 3. It is evident that the maximum yearly strain variation appears to be less than 300 microstrains of difference between the highest and lowest values. Furthermore, the overall maximum annual variation sums up to less than 400 microstrains. Evidently, this maximum strain difference of 400 microstrains due to temperature variation during the designated period correlates with the magnitude of a single truck loading on the bridge.

In addition to the preceding long-term monitoring plan, several short-term load tests have been performed on the Tech 21 Bridge to date. These live-load tests, conducted at different times of the year to verify the influence of climate changes in the ambient temperature, involved temporary instrumentation setups to monitor strain and deflection responses to controlled loading configurations. The loads were applied via two trucks, driven across the bridge at crawl speed, with different axle configurations and weights. The details of these tests are furnished in [3].

A typical response history of the bridge structure, subjected to the crawling truck load in January 2000 tests, is presented in Figure 4. It is apparent that the maximum response at this measurement point is less than 250 microstrains. This crawl speed test result appears to be consistent with the stationary truck test response. Hence, it provides a conceptual measure of the healthy bridge-performance, comparable to previous live-load test measurements.

Figure 3. Typical Temperature Sensor Monitoring Over 44 Months.

Figure 4. Bridge Response Due to Truck Load Test at Crawling Speed.

CONCLUSIONS

The Tech 21 Bridge, the nation's third and Ohio's first all-composite vehicular bridge, has provided researchers invaluable field data concerning performance of FRP composites for civil engineering applications. It has also served as a vehicle for collaboration amid several entities including academe, industry, and government. Furthermore, it has provided means of effective technology transfer from defense industry to the civil infrastructure.

Results of a series of short-term load tests performed on the Tech 21 Bridge have revealed that the strength of the advanced composite materials is far greater than that utilizing conventional bridge building materials. Also, the rating is controlled entirely by the deflection criterion. These tests also validated the design parameters by providing correlations with design analysis results, and by demonstrating that the measured strains and corresponding stresses were well within material limits.

The long-term structural health-monitoring program has provided a better insight concerning the durability of the FRP composite materials for civil engineering construction. The structural response regarding the composite deck and associated U-beams are within acceptable strain levels under the daily and yearly effects of alternating temperature cycles.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors wish to acknowledge the assistance of following organizations for their contributions at various stages of implementation, load-testing, health-monitoring, and analyses:

- Bridge Diagnostics, Inc.
- Foster-Miller
- LJB Engineers
- Martin Marietta Materials
- Wright-Patterson Air Force Base

In addition, the invaluable contributions of Dr. Fredrick Stoll (formerly with the University of Dayton Research Institute, UDRI) and Dr. Daniel Farhey (University of Dayton) are greatly appreciated.

REFERENCES

1. Better Roads, "Bridge Inventory 2002," <http://www.betterroads.com/articles/bridgeinv02.htm>, Accessed July 23, 2002.
2. Cooper, J.D. and Munley, E., "Bridge Research: Leading the Way to the Future," in Public Roads, Summer 1995, pp. 23-27.
3. Foster, D.C., "Fabrication, Installation, and Health-Monitoring of the Tech 21 Composite Material Highway Bridge," Butler County, Ohio, Final Report Published by the Butler County Engineer's Office, November 1998, 68 p.
4. Griffiths, J.R., "Plastic Highway Bridges," <http://www.csa.com/hottopics/bridge/overview.html>, Accessed July 17, 2001.
5. Hooks, J.M., and Cooper, J., "Federal Sponsorship of Innovative Bridge Programs," <http://www.nabro.unl.edu/articles/20002012/download/Hooks.pdf>, Accessed November 18, 2002.
6. Market Development Alliance (MDA) of FRP Composites Industry, <http://www.mdacomposites.org/>, Accessed September 10, 2002.
7. Martin Marietta Composites, "DuraSpan Composite Bridge Deck – Bridge Technology for the 21st Century," www.martinmarietta.com, Accessed February 12, 2002.
8. Richards, D., Solomon, G., Jack, R., Thomson, D., and Dumlao, C., "Review of Field Data on the All-Composite Highway Bridge, Tech 21," Proceedings of the Composite Institute's International Composites EXPO, May 10-12, 1999, 6p.
9. "Tech 21 Bridge Fact Sheet: Ohio's 1st All Composite Bridge," <http://www.bceo.org/technology.html>, Accessed March 12, 2001.
10. Thomson, D., "A Composite Bridge Health-Monitoring System, Final Report Prepared by Foster-Miller, Inc., for the Wright Laboratory, June 1999, 93p.